

DETERMINATION OF MODE II INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS ENHANCEMENT OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBER-REINFORCED MATRIX COMPOSITES WITH GRAPHENE AND MULTI-WALLED CARBON NANOTUBES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre-reinforced composites are widely applied in various engineering fields and have exposed specific stress-bearing shortages under strong impact in different environment. So, composites with interlaminar toughness enhancement methods have been considered. In this paper, the carbon fibre-reinforced composites' interlaminar fracture toughness is tested with two kinds of complements under two different densities adding in the middle layer based on those nano materials' toughness enhancement conclusions that former researchers have obtained. The specimens' scale satisfied the ASTM D7905/7905M-14 standard and all the experiment process is conducted under the standard conditions. All the data from the specimens are considered to be valid, but given that the too-low or too-high value may contain accidental factors, both the highest and lowest values are deleted during the data processing. From the results, the MWCNTs group under the 1.0g/m² adding density behaved better than the Graphene group compared with the Control group and the energy release rate increased 138.04% and 88.70% respectively, which is very pleasant. While for the 0.5g/m² adding density, neither the MWCNTs nor the Graphene obtained enhancement, which means that the density is not suggested. The toughness enhancing mechanism is analysed to be the more energy release needed when pulling the MWCNTs out and the adhesive among the nano materials and matrix.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber-reinforced composites has merits like high modulus and strength, much lighter than most kinds of alloy and be eco-friendlier. It is widely used in engineering field, and have been taking up an increasing rate on the structural materials choosing, especially in aeronautical and astronautical industries. But, the interlaminar toughness of unidirectional tape remains a relatively low degree, especially when serving in an environment under relatively high impact pressure, which is not so pleasant and the composites are easy to have cracks [1]. And safety and reliability of the composites in practical application would be improved if this problem were solved, which will lead to a wider application in various fields with good effect.

Lots of researchers have made their efforts to improve the interlaminar fracture toughness from different degrees or academic fields in the last several decades and many effective methods have been carried out to enhance the toughness of composites to the high value nowadays [2]. By treating the interlamination differently, Madhukar (1992) changed the level of adhesion between fiber and matrix of the graphite fiber/epoxy system [3]. Under the same improving mechanism, using heat-treated interface modification can enhance the carbon composites, which was conducted by Sun (2018) [4]. Besides the chemical methods like treating the interlamination and changing its substance properties of chemical degrees, most of the researchers tried the physical methods.

Graphene have been highly focusing on in recent years after it has been obtained by the Manchester team led by Andre Geim and Kostya Novoselov, for its unique electron structure and two-dimension properties [5]. In addition, the multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), which made from graphitic carbon needles, the particle of it can be as small as a 2.2 nm, and usually at an average of 4.8-5.5 nm [6]. So, carbon fiber-reinforced composites with graphene or MWCNTs supplements were designed and the toughness changes were tested. Using MWCNTs with several densities has been shown a positive toughness reinforced effect by Quan et al. (2018) [7].

However, the effect of using graphene is seldom researched, and the optimal supplementation of both of them are not clear as well. The research work is to obtain a more detailed toughness enhancement effect of using MWCNTs and graphene. So, two kinds of supplements are added into the interlaminar of Mode II specimen under two different densities in this experimental research. Obvious toughness enhancement under shearing load are obtained for MWCNTs with 1.0 g/m^2 density, while energy release rate of Mode I is maintained. Besides, because of the different batches of the specimen material, the properties of them exist differences to some extent.

2 MATERIALS OF THE SPECIMENS

T700 carbon fibres are chosen as the reinforced agent, which are fabricated by Toray company, and the matrix is thermosetting epoxy resin. The adding nano-materials are multi-layers graphene and multi-walled carbon nanotubes. MWCNTs are prepared by chemical vapor deposition, and its purity is greater than 95wt% with an inner diameter of 3-5nm and external diameter of 8-15nm. The length of MWCNTs is 3-12 μm . The multi-layer graphene's purity is 95wt% with a thickness of 3.4-8nm, and its diameter is 5-50 μm . Each graphene nanoplate is composed of 5-10 layers. According to the experimental design, composites laminates are composed of 30 layers of 0° ply.

3 EXPERIMENT STANDARDS

Fig. 1 shows the schematic diagram of experimental equipment. And the sizes of the specimen which are denoted by different letters have the corresponding values of $L=50\text{mm}$, $B=25\text{mm}$, and $2h=4\text{mm}$ respectively. The pre-cracked length is around 35mm in order to conduct the End Notched Fracture (ENF) by putting plastic films before spraying the toughening agent on the middle ply and solidifying those prepregs. The Mode II fracture toughness test of carbon fiber epoxy matrix composites was carried out in this experiment under the standard of ASTM D7905/7905M-14[8].

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of experimental equipment.

For the energy releasing rate calculation, the widely used formula is shown as follow [9],

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9P^2 a^2}{16B^2 E_1 h^3} \left(1 + 0.2 \frac{E_1}{G_{13}} \left(\frac{h}{a} \right)^2 \right) \quad (1)$$

Where P is the critical load, a is the crack length, B is the width, 2h the specimen thickness, E_1 denotes the longitudinal modulus and G_{13} denotes the interlaminar shear modulus. Given that the calculation convenience and the material's properties, the interlaminar shear modulus of the specimens is unknown. This formula could be used as a kind of check tool to check whether the energy release rate by another method is convincing if further study needs the details of the material's properties.

In order to avoid this value calculating, the Russell's formula is chosen, which is very similar to formula (1). According to the Russell's formula [10], the energy release rate can be calculated as follow. This formula has been used widely in fracture mechanics, which proves that this formula's accuracy and effectiveness.

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9P^2 a^2}{16B^2 h^3 E_{11}} \quad (2)$$

Wherein, G_{IIc} denotes the Mode II energy release rate, P denotes the critical load, a denotes the crack length, B denotes the specimen width, h denotes the specimen half-thickness, and E_{11} denotes the modulus of elasticity of the 0° unidirectional tape material.

4 TEST RESULTS

Form the test, three groups of figures have been obtained and the particular analysis will be conducted in each group. The figure in the left side has a complement adding density of 1.0g/m^2 while in the right shows the half-down density's results. Obvious differences can be found among the comparison.

4.1 Force-Displacement Analysis

Three groups of valid data have been chosen from the 1.0g/m^2 Control (will be called as 1.0Control) and 0.5g/m^2 Control (will be called as 0.5Control, the other two kinds will be named in the same way) each, which is convenient to make comparison. The average maximum force of the 1.0Control is around 800N and it is lower than the 0.5Control, which is about 900N under a very small standard deviation. The No. 3, which is in the left side of the Fig. 2, has an extremely small maximum force has a different length of the plastic film that influence the behavior of it. But this data can be considered as valid because the length of the plastic film will be thought when using the Russell's formula. The processes of each specimens are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Force-Displacement of the Control Group.

Both 1.0MWCNTs and 0.5MWCNTs obtained satisfied results from the experiment. As shown in Fig. 3, the increase of the maximum force a specimen can bear can be obviously seen. For the 1.0 MWCNTs, the average value is around 1300N with one specimen has a different line slope and that may be caused by the length of the plastic film, which is a little bit longer than other. For the 0.5MWCNTs, the average value of force is about 900N and compared with the 0.5Control, it is just remained.

Figure 3: Force-Displacement of the MWCNTs Group.

Fig. 4 shows the behavior of the Graphene group and both two groups obtained the data in a low fluctuation. On the left side, the 1.0Graphene’s average value is around 1000N while on the right side, 800N. According to the Russell’s formula, for the specimens have same scale and the length of the plastic films are considered to be the same, the force can represent its energy release rate. So, the 0.5Graphene did not behaved pleasantly and the energy release rate may be decreased a little.

Figure 4: Force-Displacement of the Graphene Group.

4.2 Energy release rate-Kind Analysis

Energy release rate calculated according to the Russell’s formula is shown in Fig. 5. On the left side, the 1.0 group has raised a lot, especially the 1.0MWCNTs, the increasing rate can reach about 100%. While on the right side, neither the 0.5MWCNTs nor the 0.5Graphene has contribute to the enhancement of the energy release rate and the 0.5Graphene’s G_{IIC} is a little bit lower than the 0.5Control.

The 1.0MWCNTs’ average energy release rate is 2039.95J/m². The toughness enhancement rate of it compared with the Original group is 138.04%. While for the 0.5MWCNTs, its average value is 1268.26J/m². The toughness enhancement rate of it is 0.96%. It is apparent that the former one has a higher average energy release rate and much better result than the latter one and this result is

correspondent with the densities' distribution. For the second MWCNTs group, the enhancing rate is considered to be 0% because the complement did not make sense.

The 1.0Graphene's average rate 1617.15J/m². The toughness enhancement rate of it compared with the Original group is 88.70%, which is lower than the increasing rate of MWCNTs, but still represents a high increasing rate. While for the 0.5Graphene, its average value is 1188.59J/m². The toughness enhancement rate of it is -5.38%, which shows no obvious improvement because of the low adding density and it do exist slight fluctuation.

Figure 5: G_{IIC}-Kind under two densities.

5 SEM ANALYSIS

After conducting the experiment, part of the specimens was scanning under the electron microscope. The following 3 figures, Fig. 6, Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, shows the details of the scanning results. The graphene fragment can be easily seen under the SEM and the left figure in Fig. 6 shows a piece of multilayer graphene fragment embedded in the interlamination. Compared with that one, the right figure shows a region of the damage surface. From that region, the multilayer graphene's crack state is peeling off and the adhesive between the graphene and matrix distribute a lot.

Fig. 7 shows the conferted appearing of MWCNTs region on the surface and the red frame emphases the multi-walled carbon nanotubes that are extremely long after pulling out to release energy. And the more fracture region with part of the MWCNTs represents a higher energy release rate from the interlamination.

The macro view of the different surfaces shows that the character of the Graphene surface is full of rough area while the Control one and the MWCNTs one has much smoother surface with carbon fiber clearly seen.

Figure 6: Graphene group.

Figure 7: MWCNTs group.

Figure 8: Control group.

6 CONCLUSIONS

- Adding graphene or multi-walled carbon nanotubes to the interlayer can improve the toughness of the composites to a certain extent, but it is closely related to the adding density, and the toughening effect is very good when the density is $1.0\text{g}/\text{m}^2$, but the toughening effect is not ideal when it is reduced to $0.5\text{g}/\text{m}^2$. It can be determined that interlayer additives do not degrade the original properties of the composites.
- At the same density, the addition effect of multi-walled carbon nanotubes is better than that of multi-layer graphene, because the extra energy required for multi-walled carbon nanotubes to pull out under the action of complex materials is more than that of multi-layer graphene being peeled off from the colloidal surface.

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